

Evolution of strengthening mechanisms in ODS 316L steel during plastic straining

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Abstract:

Oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) austenitic steels are attractive candidates for high-temperature structural applications, therefore, it is necessary to fully understand evolution of their strengthening mechanisms. In this work, conventional 316L and ODS 316L steels are fabricated by powder metallurgy and mechanical alloying. Combination of tensile, repeated stress relaxation and unloading compressive tests are combined with constitutive models to describe the activity of strengthening mechanisms during plastic straining in both materials. The description of strengthening mechanisms is complemented with SEM/TEM observations. The results reveal that in ODS 316L both yield strength and strain hardening are dominated by long-range internal stresses arising from grain boundaries and geometrically necessary dislocations. Oxide particles provide the significant short-range strengthening contribution at yield point but act as relatively weak obstacles during plastic flow. Their primary role being stabilization of the ultrafine-grained structure. In conventional 316L, short-range strengthening is governed by solid solution and statistically stored dislocations, while strain hardening is associated with the progressive build-up of long-range back stress caused by the formation of dislocation cell structures.

Keywords

ODS 316L, dislocations, strengthening, constitutive models, mechanical testing

1. Introduction

Oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) austenitic steels have attracted increasing attention as structural materials for high-temperature and radiation-demanding environments, such as advanced nuclear reactors and energy systems [1][2][3]. The ODS austenitic steels combine mechanical strength, creep resistance, and thermal stability, resulting from the homogeneous dispersion of nanoscale oxide particles—typically Y–Ti–O or Y–Al–O complexes—within a face-centered cubic (FCC) matrix [4][5][6][7]. Compared with ferritic and ferritic–martensitic ODS steels, the austenitic ODS variants offer enhanced ductility, fracture toughness, and corrosion resistance due to their FCC crystal structure, which provides a higher number of active slip systems and lower diffusivity of substitutional solutes [8][9][10].

The mechanical behavior of different types of ODS austenitic steel was extensively studied, and different effects were analyzed. An influence of processing route was studied [11], showing that a combination of hot isostatic pressing with forging improves ductility [12], and extrusion produces smaller grains compared to hot-rolling [13]. Tensile properties were evaluated at room temperature [14][15], as well as at elevated temperatures [16][17][18][19]. High temperature creep test revealed microstructural stability of ODS austenitic steels [9][10].

The strength of ODS steels is the result of interactions of dislocations with different microstructural features such as solute atoms, dispersed particles, dislocation forest and grain boundaries. The

assessment of individual mechanisms was performed by several studies for the estimation of yield stress [7][9][20][21]. However, the description of strengthening mechanisms during the plastic straining is a more complex task. The evolution of plastic deformation and dislocation density during tension was measured by in-situ synchrotron experiments [5][6][14]. Dislocation movement through the field of obstacles was also observed by in-situ transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [22] or by TEM images at different stages of plastic deformation [23][24]. These experimental methods are limited by observation of local conditions. The analysis of deformation mechanisms during plastic straining on a global scale can be performed by the combination of specific mechanical tests and phenomenological models of dislocation-microstructure interactions. The tensile test can be analyzed using constitutive relation analysis (CRA) derived by Saimoto and Van Houtte [25], which was applied on FCC metals [26][27] and dispersion-strengthened FCC metals [28]. The effects of short and long-range dislocation interactions can be analyzed using the division of flow stress into effective and back stress. Such a division can be made using an unloading test, which can find forward and reverse yield points [29][30]. This method was used for the description of strengthening mechanisms in ferritic steels [31] and austenitic steels [24]. The thermal activation of dislocations and short-range interactions can also be analyzed using repeated stress relaxation tests. The method was proposed by Spätig et al. [32] and applied to FCC metals [33][34] and ODS ferritic steel [35][36].

In this study, a combination of advanced mechanical testing, phenomenological modeling of dislocation–microstructure interactions, and TEM observations is employed to elucidate the strengthening mechanisms operating during plastic straining in conventional and ODS 316L steels produced by powder metallurgy.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Material

Two testing materials were fabricated using the mechanical alloying method. Conventional 316L steel (CVN) and oxide dispersion-strengthened 316L steel (ODS). Both materials were fabricated from gas-atomized AISI 316L stainless steel powder with a particle median size of $d_{50} = 27.6 \mu\text{m}$ (Sandvik Osprey Ltd., UK). The ODS material was created by the addition of Titanium (0.3 wt.%, 99.7% purity, $d_{50} = 150 \mu\text{m}$, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and yttrium (0.24 wt.%, 99.5% purity, $d_{50} = 400 \mu\text{m}$, Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Mechanical alloying was performed in a planetary ball mill (Pulverisette P-6, Fritsch, Germany) using a hardened steel vial (tool die steel 62SiMnCr4, EN 1.2101) with 25.4 mm steel balls (bearing steel 100Cr6, EN 1.3505) for 24 h under vacuum. The ball-to-powder weight ratio was 15:1, and the rotation speed of the central disc was set to 350 rpm. After milling, the powder was sieved to obtain particles smaller than $50 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting powders were consolidated by Spark Plasma Sintering (TT SPS 10-4, Thermal Technology LLC, USA) at 1150°C and uniaxial pressure of 80 MPa with a dwell time of 20 min. The dispersion of oxidic nanoparticles was created during the SPS process by the internal oxidation process, which involves residual oxygen naturally present on the surface of metallic particles and residual oxygen from the milling atmosphere. A more detailed description of material processing can be found in [37].

The electron microscopy was used to analyze the microstructure and chemical composition of the materials. Scanning electron microscopy was performed by SEM - LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEM, (Tescan, Czech Republic) equipped with EBSD and EDS detectors, operated with Aztec software (Oxford Instruments, UK). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was accomplished by SEM – Helios NanoLab, (FEI, Czech Republic) equipped with gallium focused ion beam (FIB), which was used for lamellae preparation. The lamellar samples were subsequently observed in the TEM microscope Titan-Themis S/TEM (FEI, Czech Republic) equipped with EDS + EELS detector.

The illustration of grain microstructure by EBSD image with the grain size distribution is shown in Figure 1. The TEM image of oxide particles and their size distribution in ODS material is shown in Figure 2. The average values of grain size and oxide particle distribution are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Average microstructural parameters of tested materials

	Conventional 316L (CVN)	ODS 316L (ODS)
Grain size d_G [μm]	11.96 ± 12.00	0.2889 ± 0.1869
Particle diameter d_{DP} [nm]	-	20.47 ± 11.09
Particles spacing l_{DP} [nm]		114.4

Figure 1: EBSD image and grain size distributions of a) CVN and b) ODS material.

a) b)
Figure 2: a) TEM image and b) histogram of size distribution of dispersed oxide particles.

2.2 Mechanical tests

Three types of uniaxial mechanical tests were performed on both materials: tensile test, repeat relaxation tensile test, and unloading compression test. All tests were executed on a universal electro-mechanical testing machine, Instron 8862 (Instron, UK), with a load capacity of up to ± 100 kN. The displacement was measured by a crosshead and a clip-on extensometer. The tests were performed at a strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and room temperature. Tensile and relaxation tests were done on a flat dog-bone-shaped specimen with gauge section dimensions of $14 \times 3 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$. The repeat relaxation tests consist of 6 cycles, 30 seconds each, at a given macroscopic strain level. The graphical representation of the repeated relaxation cycles is shown in Figure 3a). The compressive tests were performed on the cylindrical specimens with a 5 mm diameter and 7 mm height. The unloading cycles in compressive experiments consist of a 30 s relaxation period followed by the unloading to 0 N force. The graphical illustration of unloading tests is shown in Figure 3b).

Figure 3: Schematic illustrations of: a) repeated stress relaxation b) stress unloading test.

2.3 Experimental data analysis

The results of mechanical tests were analyzed to describe the evolution of plasticity and its mechanisms.

Constitutive relation analysis

The tensile tests were evaluated by the constitutive relation analysis (CRA) developed by Saimoto and Van Houtte [25], which is able to describe the evolution of dislocation structures and their interactions with other microstructural features. The method is based on the comparison of the energy expended during plastic deformation W_{exp} and energy stored in retained dislocations W_{stor} . The relation is $W_{exp} = A \cdot W_{stor}$, where A is the annihilation factor. The mean slip distance of dislocation (λ) is defined as:

$$\lambda = \frac{\phi b \mu^2}{2\tau \partial \tau / \partial \gamma} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi = \frac{2\alpha \theta_{cal}}{\mu} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \left[\left(\frac{P}{4A} \right) (2 + \beta) (\alpha \mu b)^2 \frac{1}{C_1 b} \right]^{1/(2+\beta)} \gamma^{1/(2+\beta)} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the calibration factor estimated from the condition $\lambda = l$ and $\theta_{cal} = \partial \tau / \partial \gamma$ at 0.2% of plastic strain. Parameter α describes the dislocations interactions, μ is the shear modulus and b is Burgers' vector. Shear stress is defined as $\tau = (\sigma - \sigma_0) / M$, where σ is the true flow stress and σ_0 is the true stress at the onset of plasticity and M is the Taylor factor. Plastic shear (γ) is related to the uniaxial plastic strain (ϵ_{PL}) as $\gamma = M \epsilon_{PL}$. The tensile curve data are divided into two or three stages and the equation (3) is fitted by parameters of σ_0 , β and P/A ratio. Parameter C_1 is fitted using the equation $\lambda = C_1 \tau^\beta$. The parameters σ_0 and P/A are estimated during the fitting of the first part (low plastic strain) of stress-strain data and remain constant during the fitting of the following sections. On the other hand, parameters β and C_1 are fitted in each section. The division into two or three stages, as well as the size of individual section is the result of a fitting process which minimizes the difference between experimental data and model predictions.

Thermal activation of dislocations

The stress relaxation tests are useful for the assessment of thermally activated dislocation mobility. The basic parameter is the apparent activation volume that is described by the equation:

$$V_a = kT \left(\frac{\partial \ln \dot{\gamma}}{\partial \tau} \right) \quad (4)$$

combining this equation with the Orowan equation $\dot{\gamma} = \rho_m b v$ gives the expression:

$$V_a = kT \left(\frac{\partial \ln \rho_m}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial \ln v}{\partial \tau} \right). \quad (5)$$

The repeated relaxation tests are able to determine the effects of mobile dislocation density and velocity on the changes in strain rate and stress described in equation (5). The assumption is the constant microstructure during the successive relaxations and only the density of mobile dislocations becomes exhausted. The unchanged microstructure is secured by the same stress level at the beginning of each relaxation cycle. The procedure is applied as follows. The first relaxation cycle is fitted by the equation:

$$\Delta \tau = - \frac{kT}{V_a} \ln \left(1 + \frac{t}{c} \right) \quad (6)$$

which yields in the estimation of apparent activation volume (V_a) and constant c . The following relaxation cycles are fitted by the equation (6) for obtaining the value of constant c_i . Stress decreases in individual cycles ($\Delta \tau_i$) are used to calculate parameter Ω :

$$\frac{1}{\Omega} = 1 - \left(\frac{kT}{V_a \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \Delta\tau_j} \right) \ln \left(\frac{\exp(-V_a \Delta\tau_n/kT) - 1}{\exp(-V_a \Delta\tau_1/kT) - 1} \right) \quad (7)$$

which is used in the equation:

$$\Omega = (1 + \beta_r)(1 + K/E) \quad (8)$$

where K is the plastic strain hardening modulus and E is the elastic modulus. The relative decrease of dislocation density and velocity during each relaxation cycle can be estimated by the equations:

$$\frac{\rho_m}{\rho_{m0}} = \left(\frac{c_i}{c_{i+t}} \right)^{\beta_r/(1+\beta_r)} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{v}{v_0} = \left(\frac{\rho_m}{\rho_{m0}} \right)^{1/\beta_r} \quad (10)$$

The detailed description is in Martin et al [33][34].

Effective and back stress analysis

The unloading experiments are able to distinguish between the effective stress (σ_{EFF}) and back stress (σ_X) as illustrated in FIGURE 3. The total flow stress (σ_{TOT}) can be written as [29][30]:

$$\sigma_{TOT} = \sigma_{EFF} + \sigma_X \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{EFF} = 0.5(\sigma_{TOT} - \sigma_R + \sigma_{TH}) \quad (12)$$

where σ_R is the reversed yield stress and σ_{TH} is the thermal stress obtained from the stress relaxation part of the test. The effective stress represents short-range dislocation interactions with dislocation forest, solute atoms and precipitates, while back stress is the result of long-range stress fields created by grain boundaries, large dislocation structures like cells and pile-ups.

3. Results

The experimental results in the form of true stress-true plastic strain curves for tensile and stress relaxation tests are shown in Figure 4. Both methods yield in similar stress-strain behavior confirming the consistency and correctness of the experimental setup. The resolution of experimental curves allows the direct estimation of yield stress σ_0 , which is used in CRA. The value of σ_0 is determined as the average value from all tensile and relaxation curves. The comparison of experimental data and results of CRA is shown in Figure 5 as shear strain vs shear stress.

Figure 4: Plastic true stress vs true plastic strain curves for tensile and stress relaxation tests of conventional (CVN) and ODS 316L steel.

Figure 5: Comparison of CRA with tensile test data for a) CVN and b) ODS material. Short solid vertical lines mark the division between different stages.

The best fit for CVN material was obtained for two stages, while ODS material required division into three stages. The results of CRA fitting are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters of CRA analysis

Material	σ_0 [MPa]	P/A	β (1)	C_1 (1) [m]	γ (1-2)	τ (1-2) [MPa]
CVN	216.9	0.1028	3.027×10^{-4}	4.910×10^{-7}	1.120×10^{-1}	48.24
ODS	786.4	0.1385	4.352×10^{-1}	2.447×10^{-9}	5.126×10^{-3}	72.82
	β (2)	C_1 (2) [m]	γ (2-3)	τ (2-3) [MPa]	β (3)	C_1 (3) [m]
CVN	-4.101×10^{-1}	1.991×10^{-6}	-	-	-	-
ODS	5.660	8.960×10^{-19}	1.366×10^{-1}	121.3	1.590	1.314×10^{-10}

The evolution of plasticity is demonstrated by the evolution of hardening modulus with shear stress, as shown in Figure 6. The hardening of CVN material decreases steeply during the first stage, followed by a slower decrease at higher plastic strain level. The ODS material has a different evolution of hardening. The modulus decreases steeply during the first two stages up to the shear stress of 100 MPa. Hardening is higher compared to CVN material. The transition between the second and third stage, the hardening is constant and decreases at a high level of plastic strain.

Figure 6: Plastic hardening modulus vs shear stress for CVN and ODS material. The vertical dashed lines represent the values of shear stress describing the boundaries of different stages in CRA.

The dislocations interactions with microstructure can be analyzed by the evolution of dislocations mean-free path and obstacle spacing with shear stress as shown in Figure 7a). The CVN material shows initial increase of mean-free path followed by a decrease. In the initial stage the dislocations are rearranging and annihilates, therefore the mean-free path increases, with increasing plasticity, the obstacle spacing decreases with mean-free path, which represents the similitude region. The ODS material shows different curve for mean-free path. The behavior at the onset of plasticity is similar to CVN material. In the first stage, the mean-free path is smaller than obstacle spacing, which refers to dislocations' rearrangement.

During the second stage, the mean-free path increases significantly and overcomes the grain size by factor of 4. At the transition between the second and third stage, the mean-free path decreases with decreasing obstacle spacing and the third stage is described by the further increase of the mean-free path. The ratio of λ/l illustrates the mutual evolution of mean-free path and obstacle spacing regardless of parameter α . Figure 7b) shows that in CVN material, the ratio linearly increases with increasing shear stress and the values ranges from 2.8 – 6.7 which suggests similar deformation mechanism throughout the plastic straining. The ODS material shows significant increase of λ/l during the second stage up to the values of 18 followed by the similitude region (λ/l constant) at the transition between the second and third stage.

The third stage shows again significant increase up to $\lambda/l = 30$. It suggests that dislocations are able to move freely inside the grains and their movement and interactions with grain boundaries influence an initiation of dislocations in the neighboring grains.

Figure 7: a) Dislocation mean-free path and obstacle spacing with respect to shear stress. b) Relative length of mean-free path versus shear stress for both materials (CVN and ODS).

The results of repeated relaxation tests are represented in Figure 8 in the form of a Haasen plot showing the relation between shear stress and k/V values. The slope of the plot represents the strain rate sensitivity of dislocation interactions, and the intercept with the vertical axis represents the effects of other strengthening mechanisms.

Both materials show the positive intercept with the k/V axis representing the effect of local thermal obstacles, such as solute atoms, on thermal dislocations mobility. The effect of solutes is more substantial for CVN material at the onset of plasticity, which is indicated by a higher slope of the plot. With increased shear stress, the slope decreases but remains constant during the whole plastic region, proving that dislocation interactions with microstructure remain of the same nature.

The ODS material has, in the first stage, similar behavior as the CVN one where the dominant mobile dislocations interactions consist of a dislocation forest and solute atoms. During the second stage, the slope increases and the intercept decreases close to the plot origin. This change signifies that dislocation interactions become more localized and that oxide particles, acting as stronger obstacles, begin to influence deformation. The mobile dislocations' interactions with the microstructure are also described in Figure 9a), which shows the relative change in mobile dislocation density and velocity during the decrease of macroscopic strain rate by the order of magnitude with respect to the shear stress. The mutual evolution of mobile dislocation density and velocity is illustrated in Figure. 9b). The CVN material has the same type of behavior throughout the whole range of plasticity. The strain rate is dominantly controlled by the dislocation velocity, which decreases by almost 90% while the dislocation density only decreases by 20% when the strain rate decreases by an order of magnitude. The ODS material has two regimes. At low stress, the strain rate is driven by the dislocation density as it decreases by 85% and velocity only by 30%. As the stress increases, the mechanism changes and the mobile dislocation density remains unchanged while the velocity decreases by 90%, which shows high permeability of dislocations through the microstructure.

Figure 8: Haasen plot of inverse value of activation volume vs. shear stress in stress relaxation experiments of both materials (CVN, ODS).

Figure 9 a) Relative values of mobile dislocation density and velocity for the decrease of strain rate by one order of magnitude with respect to applied shear stress. b) Correlation of relative mobile dislocation density and velocity for decrease of strain rate by an order of magnitude. The solid line represents equation (10).

The results of unloading experiments are shown in Figure 10, where the division of flow stress into effective (σ_{EFF}) and back stress (σ_X) components is illustrated. The effective stress remains constant during the plastic strain for both materials with higher values for the ODS material. The back stress increases in both cases and becomes dominant at higher plastic strain levels, suggesting that long-range dislocations interactions are the main reason for hardening in both materials.

Figure 10: Evolution of effective stress (σ_{EFF}) and back stress (σ_{χ}) with applied plastic strain for both materials (CVN, ODS).

4. Discussion

The results show different evolution of hardening and imply different strengthening mechanisms during plastic straining in both materials. In order to describe and understand the effects of different strengthening mechanisms, the mechanical behavior of both materials is divided into two parts: yield behavior and strain hardening.

4.1 Yield strength

The stress level at the yield point can describe an initial state of microstructure and a combination of obstacles that affect the initial dislocations' motion. The assumed strengthening mechanisms are: solid solution strengthening, dislocation forest strengthening, grain boundary strengthening and oxide dispersion strengthening (in the case of ODS material). These mechanisms can be estimated using the following equation. The solid solution strengthening is given by the relation:

$$\sigma_{SS} = \sum_i K_{ci} w_i \quad (13)$$

where K_{ci} is the constant and w_i is the weight fraction of given solute atoms in the alloy. The values of individual parameters are taken from Eliasson et al [38]. The dislocation forest strengthening is described by the Taylor equation:

$$\sigma_{DF} = M\alpha\mu b\sqrt{\rho} \quad (14)$$

where ρ is the dislocation forest density ($M = 3.06$, $\alpha = 0.4$, $\mu = 77$ GPa, $b = 0.258$ nm for 316L steel [23] [39][40]). The dislocation can be divided into statistically stored dislocations (SSDs) and geometrically necessary dislocations (GNDs). Therefore, the strengthening by dislocation forest can also be divided into two components. Grain boundary strengthening is described by Hall-Petch relation:

$$\sigma_{GB} = \frac{k_{GB}}{\sqrt{d_G}} \quad (15)$$

where the k_{GB} is constant and d_G is the average grain size for given material ($k_{GB} = 0.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ [41]). The dispersed particle strengthening in ODS steels can be described by the equation taken in the form [42]:

$$\sigma_{DP} = 0.8M\alpha_{DP}\mu b/l_{DP} \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha_{DP} = -0.017 + 0.374 \log(d_{DP}/4b) \quad (17)$$

where d_{DP} is the particles diameter and l_P is the particle spacing. The values of estimated stress for each mechanism for both materials are shown in Table 3. The dislocation densities are estimated from Feugas et al. [23] and Miao et al. [6], statistically stored dislocations have a density of $5 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and geometrically necessary dislocations have a density of $5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$. The ODS material has an ultra-fine-grained structure and it can be supposed that the GNDs are distributed in the whole volume of each grain. Therefore, the same value of density is used for both SSDs and GNDs.

Table 3: Stress values for individual strengthening mechanisms during yield.

Mechanism	CVN	ODS
Solid solution (σ_{SS}) [MPa]	82	82
SSDs (σ_{DFS}) [MPa]	54 ($\rho_{SSD} = 5 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-2}$)	169 ($\rho_{SSD} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)
GNDs (σ_{DFG}) [MPa]	169 ($\rho_{GND} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)	169 ($\rho_{GND} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)
Grain boundary (σ_{GB}) [MPa]	86	557
Dispersed particles (σ_{DP}) [MPa]	-	197

The short-range interaction mechanisms are solid solution, dislocation forest of SSDs (σ_{DFS}) and dispersed particles, while long-range mechanisms are grain boundary strengthening and the effect of GNDs (σ_{DFG}). The predictions of the described models can be compared with the effective stress and back stress estimated from unloading experiments. In the fine-grained materials, the mechanisms are not independent, therefore, the root mean square RMS summation of strengthening effects is applied [43][44][45].

$$\sigma_{EFF} = \sqrt{\sigma_{SS}^2 + \sigma_{DFS}^2 + \sigma_{DP}^2} \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_X = \sqrt{\sigma_{GB}^2 + \sigma_{DFG}^2} \quad (19)$$

The comparison of model estimates with experimental data at plastic strain of 2×10^{-4} at the onset of plastic deformation is shown in Table 4. The correlation between model estimates and measured data is quite good, which shows the dominating effect of long-range interactions in the case of ODS material.

Table 4: Comparison of model estimates and experimental measurements of effective stress and back stress at plastic strain of 2×10^{-4} for CVN and ODS material.

	CVN		ODS	
	Experiment	RMS model	Experiment	RMS model
Effective stress (σ_{EFF}) [MPa]	103.6	98.2 ($\rho_{SSD} = 5 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-2}$)	297.0	272.2 ($\rho_{SSD} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)
Back stress (σ_X) [MPa]	150.3	189.9 ($\rho_{GND} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)	594.2	582.1 ($\rho_{GND} = 5 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)

The predictions of models correspond with the experimental measurements, showing that in the case of CVN material, the most dominant mechanisms are solid solution strengthening for short-range interactions and GNDs for long-range ones. The ODS material shows a significant prevalence of long-

range interactions, which is mostly driven by the effects of grain boundaries. The dispersed particles provide the strongest strengthening effect in terms of short-range interactions. However, it is comparable with the effect of a dislocations forest.

4.2 Strain hardening

The evolution of strengthening mechanisms with plastic strain can also be deduced from the effects of short-range and long-range interactions on flow stress. The description of plastic properties is first analyzed for CVN material. Figure 10 illustrates that in the case of CVN material, the effective stress remains constant and hardening is dominantly driven by the back stress during plastic straining. The most significant effect in the long-range stress fields is the GNDs that accumulate in the vicinity of grain boundaries.

The dislocation mean-free path decreases together with obstacle spacing, which resembles the similitude regime. However, the ratio of λ/l increases with increasing plastic strain, which is the result of increased back stress, which helps dislocations to overcome more obstacles during the slip event. The short-range interactions are the combination of solute and dislocation forest strengthening. In the first stage of straining ($\tau < 48$ MPa), the density of mobile dislocations is relatively low, so the strain rate is influenced by their trapping, which can reach up to 50% as shown in Figure 9a.

With increased plastic strain, the mobile dislocation density increases and the effect of their trapping diminishes in a way that 80% of mobile dislocations move freely inside the microstructure. Stabilization of the interaction mechanism can be related to the transition from stage 1 to stage 2 in CRA. Because only a small fraction of mobile dislocations becomes trapped, there must be a strong annihilation mechanism present inside the microstructure. Such a mechanism can be quantified by the annihilation factor A , introduced in equation (3). The annihilation factor represents the ratio between the density of mobile dislocations needed for accommodation of plastic strain and the density of retained dislocations. It can be calculated according to the equation [26]:

$$A = \left(\frac{\mu\gamma}{4\pi\tau Z} \right)^2 \quad (20)$$

where Z is the number of active slip systems ($Z = 6$ is typical for FCC). The course of factor A is shown in Figure 11. For the CVN material, the factor A increases with shear stress up to the value of 25, confirming that most of the mobile dislocations are annihilated during plastic deformation. Factor A linearly increases with *the* λ/l ratio, showing that with increasing stress and obstacle density, the annihilation of mobile dislocations becomes a significant mechanism.

The geometric nature of dislocations interactions can be described by the factor P , which can be deduced from knowledge of *the* P/A ratio (equation 3) and A (equation 20). The factor $P = \gamma(\lambda)/x(\lambda^2)$, where γ is the length of the new dislocation segment that covers area x . The percolation motion of dislocations through the field of obstacles results in $P = 0.2$, while the creation of cell structures is signaled by $P = 2$ and higher. In general, weaker obstacles have $P < 1$ while stronger ones *have* $P > 1$ [26][46]. The plot of P factor is shown in Figure 12. The CVN material has a steadily increasing value of P reflecting the increasing strength of the obstacle field rising from the increasing dislocation density. At stress level above 175 MPa, the cell structures are created, which is demonstrated by the $P > 2$, but also by an increase in λ/l ratio due to the increased mean-free path inside dislocations cells. The dislocations cells and GNDs accumulated at grain boundaries are illustrated by TEM image shown in Figure 13a). The dislocation structures appear only at a later stage of plastic strain compared to the cast produced 316L [23][41]. The reason is the grain size of $\approx 12 \mu\text{m}$, which is at the limit between large-grain size and nanocrystalline behavior [47].

The plastic processes in ODS material are more complex. The back stress produced mainly by the grain boundaries is the dominant driving force for dislocations motion. The effective stress remains constant, showing that the effect of local interactions does not change. At the first stage, the mean free path is smaller than the obstacle spacing, and the change of activation volume is similar to that of

the CVN material. The mobile dislocations interact mostly with solute atoms and the dislocation forest. In the second stage, with increasing plastic strain, the dispersed particles become more relevant and major local obstacles for dislocations as represented by the increase of Haasen plot slope.

However, the mean-free path significantly increases and overcomes the grain size, showing that dislocations, despite the local interactions, travel through the whole volume of the grain and even trigger dislocations in the neighboring grains. The easy dislocation mobility is also demonstrated by their effect on the strain rate, which is determined by the dislocation velocity. Similarly, the annihilation and geometrical factors A and P have very low values, pointing to percolation with negligible annihilation (see Figures 11 and 12). At the end of the second phase, the region “similitude” is established, where λ/l becomes constant and factors A and P increase; however, they still remain in the regime of percolation with low annihilation rate in the range 1-3.

The calculation of both factors is extended for $Z = 4$, which represents the minimum number of active slip systems [26]. The similarity region can be related to the transition of the relative strength of individual mechanisms. The back-stress corresponding to plastic strain at stages 2-3 transition is 952.4 MPa (see Tab R1 and Figure 10). Using equation (19) and $\sigma_{GB} = 557$ MPa gives the strengthening of GNDs equal to 772.5 MPa, which is an opposite situation in strengths compared to the yield point.

Therefore, the region of similitude and stages 2-3 transition can be related to the transition from dominant grain boundary effect to dominant GNDs effect. The third stage of plastic straining is characterized by the further increase of the mean-free path, which is caused by the increase in long-range driving force. The GNDs and mobile dislocation densities increase, resulting in more interactions, which is reflected by the increased annihilation factor A . The geometrical factor P remains smaller than one, showing that the obstacles against dislocation motion remain weak. Figure 13b) illustrates the dislocation structures inside grains of the ODS material. There are no complex dislocation structures inside the grains, and there is a high concentration of dislocations at the grain boundaries.

In summary, the deformation behavior of CVN material initial strength is given equally by the SSDs and GNDs in combination with grain boundaries. The evolution of microstructure during plastic deformation follows the similitude effect with significant mobile dislocations annihilation and creation of dislocation cell structures at the extended plastic deformation. On the other hand, the ODS material has high initial strength caused dominantly by GNDs and grain boundaries. Such a high stress level creates a significant driving force for mobile dislocations, which are able to freely travel through the whole grain from one grain boundary to another. The dispersed oxide particles make the dominant obstacle for short-range dislocation interactions. However, they can still be counted as weak obstacles compared to the effect of grain boundaries and GNDs.

Figure 11: a) Evolution of annihilation parameter A with shear stress for both materials. b) Evolution of the parameter A with the ratio λ/l .

Figure 12: Evolution of geometrical parameter P with respect to shear stress a) and the ratio λ/l for both materials. Value $P = 0.2$ represents the percolation dislocation motion through the field of obstacles, $P = 1$ is the limit for strong obstacles and $P = 2$ signifies the creation of dislocation cell structures.

Figure 13: a) TEM image of dislocation structures in CVN material. The descriptions show examples of grain boundary, dislocation cell and GNDs. b) TEM image of microstructure of ODS material after plastic straining. The image illustrates the concentration of GNDs at the grain boundaries.

5. Conclusions

The study presents the plastic deformation mechanisms of the 316L austenitic steel with and without oxide dispersion particles manufactured by powder metallurgy. The results can be summarized into the following points:

- The conventional 316L created by powder metallurgy behaves similarly to the standard cast materials with the same deformation mechanisms.
- The ODS 316L steel has an ultra-fine-grained microstructure.
- The yield stress in ODS material is mostly driven by the grain boundary effect and GNDs effects.
- The dominating influence on flow stress arises from the long-range dislocation interactions.
- Conventional (CVN) material hardens by the interactions with grain boundaries and GNDs and trapped mobile dislocations, which create cell structures at high plastic strains.
- ODS material hardens by the interaction of dislocations with grain boundaries and GNDs in their vicinity. The oxide particles do not create strong obstacles during plastic deformation.
- The main role of oxide particles is in fixing the grain boundaries and creating an ultrafine-grained microstructure.
- Increasing the effect of particles on strain hardening leads to increasing their density or increasing the grain size.

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